

Some Lanthanide-EDTA Ternary Complexes with Protocatechuic and β -Resorcylic Acids

S. N. LIMAYE and M. C. SAXENA*

Department of Chemistry, Dr. H. S. Gour Vishwavidyalaya, Sagar-470 003

Manuscript received 10 November 1983, revised 11 April 1985, accepted 31 July 1985

The metal ligand stability constants of 1 : 1 binary and 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complexes of some lanthanides have been determined pH-metrically using Irving-Rossotti titration technique. The ternary systems under study are of the type LN-EDTA-L, where LN=La^{III}, Ce^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III} and Sm^{III}; L=protocatechuic (pca), or β -resorcylic (β -resa) acid.

The general trend of stability constants has been found to be, $\log K_{MA}^M \gg \log K_{ML}^M > \log K_{MAL}^{MA}$. The values of $\Delta \log K$ are negative due to electrostatic repulsion involved in the formation of the ternary complexes. The sequence of stability constants with respect to the metal ions has been found to be La^{III} < Ce^{III} < Pr^{III} < Nd^{III} < Sm^{III}, whereas that with respect to the secondary ligands is pca > β -resa. Two stability parameters, % relative stabilisation and % relative astatisticality, have been introduced to compare the relative stabilisation and relative astatisticality, respectively, of the ternary complexes.

The validity of Born relation has been tested. Stability correlations have been discussed with standard entropies, standard redox potentials and sum of the first three ionisation potentials of the lanthanides. Log-log relations have been discussed mathematically.

STABILITY constants of 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complexes of the type M^{III}-A-L, where M^{III}=Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II} or Cd^{II}; A=EDTA⁴⁻, dipyriddy⁴⁻, or *o*-phenanthroline³⁻, and M^{III}-A-L, where M^{III}=La^{III}, Pr^{III} or Nd^{III}; A=NTA⁴⁻, EDTA⁴⁻ or CDTA⁶⁻; and L=phenols and phenolic acids, have been reported by us and other workers. Stability constants of binary β -resorcylic acid chelates⁷ are also reported in literature. The present work deals with the determination of the stability constants of 1 : 1 binary and 1 : 1 : 1 ternary lanthanide complexes using EDTA as primary ligand and protocatechuic acid (pca), or β -resorcylic acid (β -resa) as secondary ligand. Some stability correlations have also been discussed.

Experimental

Standard solutions of protocatechuic and β -resorcylic acids were prepared in double-distilled water. The lanthanide solutions were prepared by dissolving the nitrates of La^{III}, Ce^{III} and Sm^{III} in water. Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} oxides were dissolved in minimum quantity of perchloric acid, excess of which was carefully evaporated and checked beforehand so as to eliminate the possibility of any extra acid in the metal ion solutions. EDTA was used as its di-sodium salt, the remaining protons were also taken care of.

The usual titration sets for the binary and ternary complexes were prepared. The ionic strength was

maintained at I=0.2 (mol dm⁻³ NaClO₄). Dilute solutions (1 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³) were used to avoid the possibility of formation of polynuclear species. The sets were titrated against 0.2 mol dm⁻³ carbonate free NaOH at 25° using Irving-Rossotti pH-titration technique⁸.

A Elico LI-120 digital pH meter was used to record pH readings.

Results and Discussion

The calculated values of proton-ligand stability constants ($\log K_n^H$) of the secondary ligands and the metal-ligand stability constants of 1 : 1 binary complexes with the secondary ligands (L) (*i.e.* $\log K_{ML}^M$) have been recorded in Table 1. The stability constants of 1 : 1 : 1 ternary complexes ($\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$) have been shown in Table 2. The free energy changes accompanying the formation of ternary complexes ($\Delta G = -2.303 RT \log K_{MAL}^{MA}$), $\Delta \log K (= \log K_{MAL}^{MA} - \log K_{ML}^M)$, overall stability constants $\log \beta_{MAL}^M (= \log K_{MAL}^{MA} + \log K_{ML}^M)$ and the displacement constant $\log K_{(d)MA}^{ML} (= \log K_{MAL}^{MA} - \log K_{ML}^M)$ have been evaluated (Table 2).

It has been found (Fig. 1, a representative set of curves) that the binary complex curve (ML) practically overlaps the ligand curve (L) in the lower pH region, which minimises the possibility of formation of any protonated species⁹. The separation of the two curves occurs at pH ~ 5.5-6.0 indicating complexation. The $\bar{n}$ values have been

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF LIGANDS AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF 1 : 1 BINARY COMPLEXES

Ligand	Proton-ligand stability constant			Metal-ligand stability constant				
	$\log K_1^H$	$\log K_2^H$	$\log K_3^H$	La ^{III}	Ce ^{III}	Pr ^{III}	Nd ^{III}	Sm ^{III}
pca(L)	10.52	8.41	4.16	7.95	8.15	8.23	8.45	8.65
β -resa(L)	9.75	2.96	—	6.09	6.21	6.34	6.48	6.58

TABLE 2—METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF 1 : 1 : 1 TERNARY COMPLEXES

Ligand		La ^{III}	Ce ^{III}	Pr ^{III}	Nd ^{III}	Sm ^{III}	
pca	$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	4.22	4.44	4.60	4.80	5.07	
	$-\Delta \log K$	3.75	3.71	3.63	3.78	3.58	
	$-\Delta G$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	20.56	21.62	22.42	23.76	24.71	
	$\log \beta_{MAL}^H$	15.75	16.27	16.75	17.41	17.90	
	$\log K_{(a)MA}^H$	3.58	3.68	3.92	4.08	4.20	
	$\log K_s$	10.64	10.91	11.17	11.51	11.80	
	R.S. (%)	47.16	45.62	44.10	44.73	41.48	
	R.A. (%)	60.34	59.30	58.82	59.29	57.08	
	β -resa	$\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$	4.06	4.18	4.19	4.33	4.47
		$-\Delta \log K$	2.01	2.07	2.15	2.13	2.11
$-\Delta G$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)		19.79	20.10	20.42	21.09	21.62	
$\log \beta_{MAL}^H$		15.49	15.96	16.34	16.86	17.30	
$\log K_{(a)MA}^H$		5.44	5.62	5.81	6.05	6.25	
$\log K_s$		10.17	10.42	10.70	11.02	11.29	
R.S. (%)		33.00	33.33	33.91	32.81	32.06	
R.A. (%)		60.07	60.36	60.84	60.71	60.40	

calculated in the pH range where no precipitation is observed.

Fig. 1. Representative pH-titration plots for (O) 1 : 1 binary LN-pca and (Δ) 1 : 1 : 1 ternary LN-EDTA-pca systems : (a) reference acid, (MA) LN-EDTA, (L) sec. ligand (pca), (ML) LN-pca, (MAL) LN-EDTA-pca and (T) theoretical composite.

The mixed complex curve (MAL) completely overlaps the curve (L) in the lower pH range, and separates from it in the region where the formation of MA is complete (*i.e.* pH 5.0-5.5). This separation of curves at sufficiently different pH range indicates the formation of mixed-complexes as, $M + A \rightleftharpoons MA$; $MA + L \rightleftharpoons MAL$. This has been further confirmed by the non-superimposable nature of the theoretical composite curve¹⁰ on the experimental mixed complex curve. The fact that the experimental values lie in the order $\log K_{MA}^M \gg \log K_{ML}^M$, minimises the possibility of any ligand displacement of the type, $MA + L \rightleftharpoons ML + A$ during the formation of mixed complexes. The $\log K_{(a)MA}^M$ values are consequently positive.

The hexadentate nature of EDTA minimises the possibility of formation of species like MA_3 or the disproportionation¹¹ of MAL into MA_2 or ML_2 . The absence of polynuclear species has been confirmed by the fact that a plot of $\bar{n}/[L]$ vs $[L]$ is a smooth curve (not shown). Calculation of % ionisation¹² reveals that the phenolic-OH is sufficiently ionised in the pH range used for calculations.

The reaction of the formation of ternary complex can be represented as,

A perusal of the values of stability constants shows that the values of $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ are lower than $\log K_{ML}^M$. This is evidently due to coulombic repulsion between the negatively charged primary complex $[\text{LN-EDTA}]^-$ and the incoming secondary ligand L^{3-} or L^{2-} . This involves further displacement of the water molecules of the remaining coordination sites and increase in additional steric strain¹³ on the ternary complex. This further contributes towards the lowering of $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ values as compared to $\log K_{ML}^M$. The $\Delta \log K$ values are consequently negative.

A quantity, % relative stabilisation (R.S.), of the ternary complexes may be defined as,

$$\% \text{ R.S.} = [(\log K_{MAL}^{MA} - \log K_{ML}^M) / \log K_{ML}^M] \times 100.$$

The numerical value of % R.S. for the two series of ternary complexes is found to vary in the range 41.5 to 47.2 for pca and 32.1 to 33.9 for β -resa.

The values of statistical stability constants ($\log K_s$, Table 2) have been calculated¹⁴ for the present set of complexes assuming lanthanide metal ion as

octacoordinate, EDTA as hexadentate and pca or β -resa as bidentate. The $\log K_s$ values are found to be greater than $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ values, which indicates the involvement of a statistical factors during the formation of mixed complexes. A quantitative measure of astatistical factors involved in the formation of mixed ligand complex may be expressed in terms of another quantity, % relative astatisticality (R.A.), which may be defined as,

$$\% \text{ R.A.} = [(\log K_s - \log K_{MAL}^{MA}) / \log K_s] \times 100.$$

The values of R.A. in the present case lie in the range 57.0 to 60.3 for pca and 60.1 to 60.8 for β -resa.

The sequence of stability with respect to the secondary ligands for binary as well as ternary complexes has been found to be, $\text{pca} > \beta\text{-resa}$, which is the order of the ligand basicity. The variation of $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ for the lanthanides shows the trend $\text{La}^{III} < \text{Ce}^{III} < \text{Pr}^{III} < \text{Nd}^{III} < \text{Sm}^{III}$, which is the order of increasing occupancy of their 4f-orbitals accompanied with a regular decrease in ionic radii, and hence a gradual increase in their ionic-potentials. The overall stability constants ($\log \beta_{MAL}^M$) also vary in the same order (Table 2). It may, however, be noted that the % variation in the ionic radii is $\sim 7.5\%$ from La^{III} to Sm^{III} , the sum of the first three ionisation potentials varies by about 11.6%, while the increase in the $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ values has been observed to lie in a rather wide range of about 20% for pca and 33% for β -resa.

Unlike the 3d-elements the lanthanides are highly electropositive with large ionic radii and their 4fⁿ-electrons are well shielded by the outer lying 5s and 5p orbitals from ligand perturbations. The metal-ligand bond should, therefore, be ionic with a minimal covalent contribution, if at all. Born relation¹⁵, $E = Z^2/2r(1-1/D)$ (where, E=energy of complexation, Z=charge and r=ionic radius of metal ion) has been tested for the present sets of ternary complexes. Plots of $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ vs Z^2/r have been found to be somewhat curved which may be due to partial covalent nature¹⁶ of the bond and varying degrees of stabilisation caused by the ligand field. Similar observations^{5,17,18} have been noted for other lanthanide complexes.

The log-log correlations for the ternary complexes have been studied quantitatively. Mathematically, the stability constants are related¹⁹ as,

$$\log K_{MAL}^{MA} = \log K_{MA}^M + (2.303 RT)^{-1} [(G_L^0 - G_M^0) + (2G_M^0 - G_{MAL}^0 - G_M^0)]$$

or,

$$\log K_{MAL}^{MA} = \log K_{ML}^M + (2.303 RT)^{-1} [(G_M^0 + G_{ML}^0) - (G_M^0 + G_{MAL}^0)]$$

It is evident from the above equations that a plot of $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ vs $\log K_{MA}^M$ or $\log K_{ML}^M$ will be linear and of unit slope, provided the second and the third terms on the right hand side of the equations are either constant or negligible. The slope will be non-unit if the third term is a linear function of the second term. These log-log plots have been found

to be linear. The best straight line plots drawn by the method of least-squares give the slope values of 1.25 and 0.65 for pca and 0.83 and 0.31 for β -resa for the two correlations MA and ML, respectively. The non-unit slope values indicate that the free-energy terms of the complexes vary smoothly and the third term is a linear function of the second term on the right hand side of the above equations.

The $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ values have been further correlated with some fundamental properties of the lanthanide metal ions, viz. standard entropy, standard oxidation potentials and sum of the first three ionisation potentials. The variation of $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ with the standard entropy (S_M^0) of the lanthanides²⁰ shows a linear increase in the stability constant with S_M^0 , indicating that the free energy changes during complexation are essentially entropy changes. Standard electrode potentials (E^0) of the present set of lanthanides, when plotted against the stability constant, yield a linear plot. The free energy change corresponding to the standard electrode potential comprises mainly the heat of formation of the bare metal ion and its heat of hydration. The latter being the heat of ligation of water molecules, one may expect a gradual increase in $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ values with decrease in the numerical value of E^0 (with increasing value of 4fⁿ) for the lanthanides.

The ionisation potential of a metal measures the energy required for the removal of valence electrons. It may also be regarded as a direct measure of the electron affinity of the metal ion whether free or combined to a ligand. Hence, a direct correlation between the stability constant and the overall ionisation potential (ΣI) of the lanthanides may be possible. The almost linear plots of $\log K_{MAL}^{MA}$ vs ΣI are in conformity with the above arguments.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. A. V. Mahajani, Head, Department of Chemistry, for providing facilities. One of the authors (S. N. L.) is thankful to U. G. C., New Delhi, for the award of a research fellowship.

References

1. I. P. MAVANI, C. R. JERURKAR and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1974, 47, 1280.
2. D. O. PATIL and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1971, 33, 529.
3. J. D. JOSHI, C. R. JERURKAR and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, 11, 940.
4. H. S. RANA and J. P. TANDON, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, 14, 914.
5. S. N. LIMAYE and M. C. SAXENA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, 59, 916.
6. H. S. RANA and J. P. TANDON, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 128.
7. S. S. DHINGRA, R. C. SHARMA and D. N. BHARGAV, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 53, 526.
8. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397; 1954, 2904.
9. S. P. TRIPATHI, G. K. CHATURVEDI and R. C. SHARMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 58, 848.
10. G. H. CAREY and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1976, 89, 2859.

LIMAYE & SAXENA : SOME LANTHANIDE-EDTA TERNARY COMPLEXES WITH PROTOCATECHUIC ETC.

11. L. C. THOMPSON and J. A. LORAAS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, 2, 89.
12. A. ALBERT and E. P. SARJEANT, "Ionisation Constants of Acids and Bases", Wiley, New York, 1962, p. 9.
13. J. L. HOARD, B. LEE and M. I. LIND, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 86, 1612.
14. R. DEWITT and J. I. WATERS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 3810; P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1981, 40, 882.
15. T. D. MOELLER, *Chem. Rev.*, 1965, 65, 1.
16. F. J. SPEDDING, D. E. POWEL and E. J. WHEELWRIGHT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 84.
17. L. K. A. STAVELY and T. RANDALL, *Farad. Discuss. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 26, 157.
18. S. N. LIMAYE and M. C. SAXENA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, 59, 698.
19. S. N. LIMAYE, Ph.D. Thesis, Dr. H. S. Gour Vishwavidyalaya, 1983.
20. F. D. DWYER and D. P. MELLOR, "Chelating Agents and Metal Chelates", Academic Press, New York, 1964.